

Gautama Buddha's commentary about Brihadaranyaka Upanishad 4.3.36 in Brahmajalasutta

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Abstract:

Bhagavan Gautama Buddha was a well-known Vedic scholar, and often quoted the Vedas. This is something which has received little attention from researchers. The idea that Bhagavan Gautama Buddha taught a contrarian and polemical worldview that was antithetical to the Vedas is a fanciful colonial legacy, which modern researchers have never bothered to examine seriously.

This paper points out how Gautama Buddha picked up Vedic verses to illustrate their secret meaning through Vedic Advaita. Gautama Buddha's interpretation will be compared with the commentary of one of the foremost Advaita teachers, Adishankaracharya.

Keywords:

Brahmajalasutta, Pali Canon, Pali Sutras, Gautama Buddha, Advaita Vedanta, Vedas

Introduction:

The Brahmajalasutta has an important discussion about the Brihadaranyaka Upanishad 4.3.36 which has received scarce focus from Buddhist scholars and researchers. The modern western understanding is that Gautama Buddha took a perspective antithetical to the Vedas and Upanishads. I examine this misguided colonial hypothesis in this analysis.

I discuss the following:

- The original Brihadaranyaka Upanishad Sanskrit verse
- The English translation of the Brihadaranyaka Upanishad Sanskrit verse
- Adi Shankaracharya's commentary
- Gautama Buddha's commentary (Sanskrit translation)
- Gautama Buddha's commentary (Anglicized interpretation)
- Gautama Buddha's commentary (English interpretation)
- Adi Shankaracharya's commentary

Discussion:

The original Brihadaranyaka Upanishad Sanskrit verse:

स यत्रायमणिमानं न्येति-जरया वोपतपता वाणिमानं निगच्छति-
तद्यथाम्रं वोदुम्बरं वा पिप्पलं वा बन्धनात्प्रमुच्यते,
एवमेवायं पुरुष एभ्योऽङ्गेभ्यः संप्रमुच्य पुनः प्रतिन्यायं प्रतियोन्याद्रवति प्राणायैव ॥ ३६ ॥

The English translation of the Brihadaranyaka Upanishad verse:

When (yatra) he (saha) reaches (nyethi) (the subtle) anima, by old age (jaraya) or (va) by proximity (upa) to afflictions (Tapa) attains (nigacchathi) (the subtle) anima indeed (va), then (that) just as (yatha) a mango (aamram) or fig (udumbara) or a sacred fig (peepal) (fruit) is detached (pramuchathe) from attachment (bandhanaath) (to the stalk), Exactly thus (evam eva), this (ayam) Purusha, completely (sam) detaches himself (pramuchya) from these (ebhya) body parts (ange) repeatedly (punah) indeed (eva) he runs (dravathi) forth (aa) towards (prathi) the natural order (Nyaya), towards (prathi) the womb (yoni) (Shakti), towards (prathi) (the source of) Prana (Pranaaya) (Shiva)

Adi Shankaracharya's commentary:

Every person attains death either by old age or by afflictions to the body. Whatever be the name and form of the body, every living being ultimately faces death. A fruit is also like a body, it can be of different shapes and colours, but it has the same inevitable fate.

The divine Purusha has forgotten who he really is. Hence, the human Purusha (who has forgotten his true nature) comes and goes, life after life, meeting the same death in the end. Whatever be the body parts, it is discarded in the end. This process continues endlessly.

What he does not recognize is that he subconsciously craves his true self (that is bereft of form), he falls towards the earth (Shakti), the source of his body, and always moves towards

the source of his Atman (Shiva). Aging is but an eternal movement towards one true parents - Shiva-Shakti. Therefore, aging has to be welcomed as it provides a chance to reunite with the mother Prakriti and father Purusha. Aging is the expression of the yearning to be united with one's true self.

In other words,

Space and time deteriorate the body. Time ripens the body and afflictions shape the shape of the body. When a body makes guttural noises before death, the sounds is that of an overloaded cart. The mind is full of unnecessary thoughts and bereft of the necessary. Owing to all this, we need to create a spirit of renunciation when we are young.

Whatever the shape of the fruit, the falling off comes through a multitude of cause. Whether winds, birds, rain or any other reason, the end result is the same. The living is always in the jaws of death. The infinite Purusha, found in the anima state of Siddhi, detaches himself from the body, just as a fruit detaches itself from the plant. The Purusha does not want to preserve the body through Prana anymore. In a state of dreaming, the Prana does the same, it retreats from the body and enters a different state. As often as we dream, we change bodies all the time. The Purusha enters a body for the fulfilment of Prana and enjoying the results of earlier Karma.

The entire universe collapses into the Purusha on death. As long as there is residual karma, the entire universe manifests in the right order to help the realization of Karma. After a dream, the Purusha returns to a body that it wants to occupy. The body happens to be the same as earlier, because the human Purusha is enamoured with the same body. With time, the attraction to the current body stops and another body begins.

Gautama Buddha's commentary (Sanskrit translation):

सेय्यथापि, भिक्षवः, आम्रपिण्ड्याः वृन्तच्छिन्नायाः यानि कानिचित् आम्राणि वृन्तप्रतिबद्धानि, सर्वाणि तानि तदन्वयानि भवन्ति;

एवमेव खलु, भिक्षवः, उच्छिन्नभवनैत्रिको तथागतस्य कायः तिष्ठति ।

यावदस्य कायः स्थास्यति, तावत् एनं द्रक्ष्यन्ति देवमनुष्याः ।

कायस्य भेदात् ऊर्ध्वं जीवितपर्यादानात् न एनं द्रक्ष्यन्ति देवमनुष्याः ॥

Gautama Buddha's commentary (Anglicized translation):

O Bhikshus, for example (seyyathaapi), if a cluster (pindi) of mangoes (aamra), whose stalks (vrnth) have been cut (chinna),

meaning (yaani) that whatsoever (kaanichith) mangoes (aamraani) are attached (prathibadh) to the stalk (vrnth), everyone (sarvaani) of those (thaani) are effected (bhavanthi) as a consequence (anvaya) of that (tat),

exactly so (evameva) indeed (khalu), O Bhikshus, when the manifestation (bhava) of the one leading (naithrik) is cut off (uchinna), the body (kaya) of the Tathagatha remains (thistathi), as long as (yaavath) the body (kaaya) of him (asya) will remain (sthaaspathi), so long (taavath) Devas and humans (manushya) will see (drishyanthi) him (enam)

after (urdhvam) the differentiation (bhedaath) of the body (kaayasya) (into its constituents) due to the exhaustion (pariyadhaan) of life (jiva), the Devas and humans (manushya) will see (drishyanthi) him (enam) no more (na).

Gautama Buddha's commentary (English interpretation):

When the stalk of a cluster of mangoes is cut, all mangoes fall down. Every mango in the cluster is impacted by the consequence of that stalk. When one of the mango (bodies) attains the highest self of Tathagatha, it is akin to the one mango detaching itself from the cycle of Samsara that the plant represents. When the leader of the cluster attains Nirvana, all others members of that cluster also attain Nirvana. The bonds binding the Tathagatha to Samsara is the same bonds tying other humans to Samsara.

The Devas and humans will see this Tathagatha as long as the body remains. Once the body breaks down into its constituents and becomes one with its creator (Shakti), the Devas and humans can no longer see his bodily form.

Conclusion:

I make five concluding points:

1. Since the Tathagatha becomes one with nature (Prakriti or Bhumadevi), worshipping Shakti is the same as worshipping the Tathagatha.
2. There is no more difference between the human, Tathagatha and the supreme Purusha at the highest point. This is nothing but the perfect non-duality of Vedic Advaita.
3. We can observe that Gautama Buddha uses the same Vedic Advaita simile of mangoes being cut from its stalk and falling to the ground. Mangoes are a very rare subject of discussion in the Vedas, Upanishads and the Pali Suttas. Hence, the logical interpretation is that Buddha was providing a commentary to the Brihadaranyaka Upanishad verse.
4. The usage of Tathagatha as a bridge between the human Purusha and the divine Purusha is observable.
5. The usage of the word "bheda" by Gautama Buddha hints that while the body disintegrates into the earth, its infinite nature merges into the infinite form of Shakti.

References:

Bhikkhu Sujato. (Trans.). (2018). The prime net of views (Brahmajālā Sutta) (DN 1). SuttaCentral. <https://suttacentral.net/dn1/en/sujato>

Appendix:

Anglicized Pali section from Brahmajalasutta (Bhikkhu Sujato, 2018):

"Seyyathāpi, bhikkhave, ambapiṇḍiyā vaṇṭacchinnāya yāni kānici ambāni vaṇṭapaṭibandhāni, sabbāni tāni tadanvayāni bhavanti; evameva kho, bhikkhave, ucchinnabhavanettiko tathāgatassa kāyo tiṭṭhati, yāvassa kāyo ṭhassati, tāva naṃ dakkhanti devamanussā, kāyassa bhedaṃ uddham jīvitapariyādānā na naṃ dakkhanti devamanussā"ti."